

Data Management Plan

Lead partner: The Cyprus Institute

Work package: D6.3 - DMP - Data Management Plan

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
GB	Gigabyte
HPCF	High Performance Computing Facility
TB	Terabyte
WP	Work Package
RDM	Research data management
GIS	Geographic Information System
LL	Living Labs
DOI	Data Object Identifier

Purpose of the deliverable

Roles and objectives to other Work Packages

Deliverable 6.3 comprises a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP), which outlines the specifics of the data that will be collected and/or generated through the entire span of the project. As it deals with all data deriving from every activity that will be performed in the context of the project, the role of the DMP is transversal to all Work Packages (WP).

Besides outlining the type, format, size, source, and purpose/utility of the data, along with its associated metadata, it also details strategies for achieving findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of information. Furthermore, it defines policies concerning data security, preservation, and ethical and legal considerations related to data sharing and assigns responsibilities to the Data Manager.

The DMP is a living document that will undergo periodic reviews at yearly intervals during the project, specifically at months 18 and 30. These reviews will ensure that the DMP remains fit for purpose both during and after the project, especially as new data accumulate.

The DUT Partnership wish to promote open, transparent and robust urban and global change research by encouraging more open sharing of research data, leading to wider data analysis, more data re-use, and the combination of datasets from multiple sources. The DUT Partnership believe that an increased emphasis on the open sharing of research data has the potential to stimulate new approaches to the collection, analysis, validation and management of data, and to the transparency of the research process.

However, the DUT Partnership also recognise that not all research data can be shared openly, and that there will be legitimate reasons to constrain access, for example the risks to the privacy of individuals must always be considered where data arise from, or are derived from, personally identifiable data.

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first version of the DMP of the project. It describes the initial plan on how data that will be collected and/or generated will be shared, archived and preserved throughout the project and also after its end. It contains information about:

- the kinds, provenance and formats of the data foreseen to be collected/generated,
- the procedures and guidelines that will be followed to ensure compliance with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) Data Management Principles¹,
- the allocation of resources required to make data FAIR,
- the procedures that will be followed to ensure data security, and
- ethical aspects and how these will be handled.

Data collected/generated will be stored to Google Drive cloud servers using a commercial, non-public license of Google Workspace that meets privacy and security requirements to comply with GDPR. The administrator of the account will ensure that access to the data will only be possible to project team members according to a Data Classification Policy that will organize them into user groups determined by the Steering Committee. The identification of the team members will be ensured by using authentication processes. Also in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)² (GDPR), a Data Region Policy will be set to ensure that data are stored exclusively to servers geographically located in Europe. Deliverables and research results of the project classified as public, as well as all scientific publications deriving from it, will be published to Zenodo open repository to provide open access, using the developed B_GREEN community.

For the preparation of the DMP the authors have used the Horizon Europe (HE) Data Management Plan (DMP) Template³ (version 1.1, 01.04.2022). In each of the following sections, a set of questions appear in rectangles at their beginning: these questions derive from the DMP template and capture the information that should be provided within the section each time.

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

³ EU Grants: Data management plan (HE):V1.1 – 01.04.2022. Accessible as a Project reporting template at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON?selectedProgrammePeriod=2021-2027&selectedProgramme=HORIZON>

1. Introduction

The project will collect relevant research data (data collected in previous scientific publications/patents, measuring data, design specifications, etc.) and associated metadata, that will be managed according to the Data Management Plan respecting the principle that open scientific research data should be easily discoverable, accessible, useable, and wherever possible interoperable to specific quality standards. This task will then consist in establishing collectively a Data Management Plan (DMP), which is a key element of good data management. An initial version of the DMP will be delivered at Month 6 and will be regularly updated.

Research data management (RDM) encompasses the processes of transformation, selection and storage of research data with the common goal of keeping them accessible, reusable and verifiable in the long term and independent of individuals.

Figure 1: Gaelen Pinnock, <http://scarletstudio.net>, CC BY-SA

2. Intellectual Property Rights

During the Project Management Work Package (WP5) and Dissemination and Communication Activities Work Package (WP6), B_GREEN team's members evaluated the IPR context for future exploitation of the Project results and outcomes by the Cyl in the context of WP3. For the use in the project as well as for any publication, results are subject to the clear acknowledgment of the project management board.

3. Data Management

The Data Management Plan was prepared by considering the current template of the "Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020".

Emphasizing that research data is actively recognized as an essential part of scientific publishing, all project data and associated metadata and documentation that are not disclosed by Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are stored in the Host Organisation's (HO) data repository (<https://repository.cyi.ac.cy/>) and will become publicly available on Zenodo wherever possible. Part of the data produced are shared and made accessible for verification and re-use, according to FAIR principles and the provisions in the Consortium Agreement (CA), while distribution of some specific data will remain limited until the relevant new know-how acquired in the project is protected so as not to endanger the interests of the industrial partners and not jeopardize the protection of project results.

Below, what follows includes the list of the data collected, processed and generated, the methodology and standards applied, which data will be made openly available and how the measures undertaken to facilitate the interoperability and reuse of research data, and how data will be curated and preserved. This includes all open hardware designs, case studies, and other project results and electronic materials.

4. Data Summary

DATA COLLECTION 1

How will the data be collected or created?	3D GIS data editing (ESRI ArcGIS Pro)
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What data will you collect or create?	.SLPK
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Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>A Scene Layer Package (SLPK) file is an openly published file format for 3D geospatial data, designed as a package for storage or exchange that captures all resources for a "scene layer" structured according to the Indexed 3D Scene Layer (I3S) specification. The I3S/SLPK specification originates from ESRI. It has been in use in products in ESRI's ArcGIS range since 2016. In September 2017, it was approved by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) as a community standard</p> <p>An I3S Scene Layer may be one of several layers in a "web scene". The following layer types are supported in ArcGIS: 3D object scene layers, Point scene layers, Integrated mesh scene layers, and Point cloud scene layers.</p> <p>The structure of an SLPK/I3S layer is a hierarchical index structure of nodes, in which each node's "payload" may contain features with associated geometry, textures and attributes. The layer type and profile define which particular geometries and attributes are required or allowed and whether textures are applicable.</p> <p>The package is based on a constrained form of the ZIP-PK format and represents the hierarchical structure in a hierarchy of folders. At the top level, the ZIP-based SLPK format holds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A metadata.json file • A 3dSceneLayer.json.gz file • A nodes folder containing all node resources in a tree structure <p>Format Specification: https://docs.ogc.org/cs/17-014r5/17-014r5.html</p>
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Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see D7.1).
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service at URL.
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	SLPK versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
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What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Data should be preserved indefinitely.
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Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
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DATA COLLECTION 2

How will the data be collected or created? GIS data editing (ESRI ArcGIS Pro)

What data will you collect or create? .shp

Documentation and Metadata

SHP is the file extension for one of the primary file types used for representation of ESRI Shapefile. It represents Geospatial information in the form of vector data to be used by Geographic Information Systems (GIS) applications. The format has been developed as open specifications in order to facilitate interoperability between ESRI and other software products. A shapefile format describes geospatial information of a data set as vector features. These vector features include: points, lines and polygons.

A standalone shp file cannot be used to make meaning of the data it contains. To do so, a shapefile makes use of following additional mandatory files:

shx file - index file

dbf file - a dBASE file that stores all the attributes of the shapes in the main file

prj file - stores project information of the file

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Header: The main File Header starts from the beginning of the file and is 100 bytes in length. Organization of this main file header along with byte position, value, type and byte order is as follows: bytes 0-3 represent the file code, 4-23 are unused, 24-27 represent the file length, 28-31 represent the version, 32-35 represent the shape type, 36-37 represent the minimum bounding rectangle, 68-83 represent the bounding box (Zmin, Zmax) and 84-89 represent the bounding box (Mmin, Mmax)

Data records: The main file header is followed by variable length records where each record consists of a fixed-length record header followed by variable-length record contents.

Record header: It contains information about the record number and content length of the record in a fixed length of 8 bytes. Bytes 0-3 represent the record number while bytes 4-7 represent the record length.

Record contents: A shapefile record contents consist of a shape type followed by the geometric data for that shape.

Technical description:

<https://www.esri.com/content/dam/esrisites/sitecore-archive/Files/Pdfs/library/whitepapers/pdfs/shapefile.pdf>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX below).
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	Shp versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
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What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Data should be preserved indefinitely.
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Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
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DATA COLLECTION 3

How will the data be collected or created?	Three-dimensional (3D) imaging data such -point clouds
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What data will you collect or create?	.E57
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Documentation and Metadata

A file with .e57 extension is a compact, vendor-neutral file format that is used for storing and exchange of three-dimensional (3D) imaging data such as point clouds, images, and metadata. Such data is often created with systems such as laser scanners. It was developed by the Data Interoperability sub-committee of the ATSM E57 Committee on 3D Imaging Systems. E57 is open source and stores 3D point data, its attributes (such as color and intensity), and 2D imagery as captured by the 3D imaging system.

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Header: The E57 header is a small, 48-byte binary structure that contains critical file-level information, such as the version number and the location of the XML section.

Hierarchy: The XML section of an E57 file describes the tree hierarchy using a subset of standard XML. This is based on eight E57 element types where each element is build up using a set of core building blocks. Five of these E57 elements are terminal types and three of these are non-terminal.

File format

The E57 file format specifications are available at ATSM website and can be referred to for developer's reference. The concept paper and technical details of E57 file format are available as reference material by Daniel Huber. The data in an E57 file is saved in a XML based hierarchical tree structure. At low level, the E57 files are saved as compressed binary files to make the file size compact.

<https://docs.fileformat.com/cad/rvt/>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	.e57 versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
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What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Three-dimensional (3D) imaging data should be preserved indefinitely.
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Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
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DATA COLLECTION 4

How will the data be collected or created?	Digital drafting (Autodesk AutoCAD)
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What data will you collect or create?	.dwg
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Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>DWG files contain user created information and includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Designs · Geometric data · Maps and photos <p>Header: The file header consists of DWG Header variables and information about Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) which is used for the error detection. Each subsection is a specialized vector where different lengths of bits are used to represent different labels. For instance, the first 6 bits of the DWG Header variable stands for the version string.</p> <p>Class Definitions: A DWG file may contain numerous classes depending upon the specific .dwg file purpose. Information such as class metadata size of class data area, class number and checksum in addition to others.</p> <p>Template: This is optional and for R15 and R15 versions, this section is below the Object Free Space section.</p> <p>Padding: The metadata is suffixed and postfixed with a specific number of bytes which makes the older AutoCAD software versions to be forward compatible to the new DWG file format.</p> <p>Image Data: The metadata for this section depends on the specific .dwg type. For R14 and R15 users, this section is optional.</p> <p>Object Data: The object data consists of a complete list of table entities, dictionary entries, etc. corresponding to the existing list of objects.</p> <p>Object Map: Location of each object in the file is specified in this section of file. Most of the metadata in this section are file handles that play a role in identification and re-rendering of the object.</p> <p>Object Free Space: This section is optional for all users</p> <p>Second Header: A duplicate of the file header section towards the end of the DWG file.</p> <p>https://www.opendesign.com/files/guestdownloads/OpenDesign_Specification_for_.dwg_files.pdf</p>
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Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.

Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	Dwg versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Design versions in dwg should be preserved indefinitely.

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.

DATA COLLECTION 5

How will the data be collected or created?	Historical Analysis & Conservation State analysis
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What data will you collect or create?	.pdf
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Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>PDF (Portable Document Format) is a free, open format for documents of any kind. PDF is developed by ADOBE and standardised as ISO 32000 and can encapsulate a complete description of a fixed-layout flat document, including the text, fonts, vector graphics, raster images and other information.</p> <p>PDF files may contain a variety of content besides flat text and graphics including logical structuring elements, interactive elements such as annotations and form-fields, layers, rich media (including video content), three-dimensional objects using U3D or PRC, etc. The PDF specification also provides information related to the encryption process of the file, digital signatures, file attachments, and metadata integration.</p> <p>Format Standard: https://pdfa.org/resource/iso-32000-pdf/</p>
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Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	PDF reports will be stored in separate files on the project cloud folder and linked to proprietary BIM model files. Naming convention specified in ANNEX applies.
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	PDF files versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
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What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	PDF reports should be preserved indefinitely.
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Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
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DATA COLLECTION 6

How will the data be collected or created?	Environmental data processing (Microsoft Excel)
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What data will you collect or create?	.xlsx
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Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>XLSX is a well-known format for Microsoft Excel documents that was introduced by Microsoft with the release of Microsoft Office 2007. Based on structure organized according to the Open Packaging Conventions as outlined in Part 2 of the OOXML standard ECMA-376, the new format is a zip package that contains a number of XML files. The underlying structure and files can be examined by simply unzipping the .xlsx file.</p> <p>A blank workbook, when extracted to its files, has the following constituent files and folders:</p>
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- [Content_Types].xml – Content types for parts within the package
- _rels (Folder) - Relationships folder
- docProps - overall document properties
- xl (Folder), including:
 - _rels
 - theme
 - worksheets
 - styles.xml
 - workbook.xml

Technical documentation:

<https://interoperability.blob.core.windows.net/files/MS-XLSX/%5bMS-XLSX%5d.pdf>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	xlsx versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Environmental data in xlsx should be preserved indefinitely.

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.

DATA COLLECTION 7

How will the data be collected or created?	Building and street Information data and technical reports (Microsoft Word)
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What data will you collect or create?	.docx
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Documentation and Metadata

.docx is a well-known format for Microsoft Word documents. Introduced from 2007 with the release of Microsoft Office 2007, the structure of this new Document format was changed from plain binary to a combination of XML and binary files. Docx files can be opened with Word 2007 and lateral versions but not with the earlier versions of MS Word which support DOC file extensions.

.docx contains document text, images, formatting, styles, drawn objects, and other document settings; commonly used to author documents in business and academic settings.

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

.docx files are created using the Open XML format, which stores documents as a collection of separate files and folders in a compressed zip package. DOCX files contain XML files and three folders, docProps, Word, and _rels, which hold the document properties, content, and relationships between the files.

.docx files are designed to make document contents accessible. For example, document text is saved using plain text files and document images are stored as individual image files within the DOCX file.

Technical documentation:

<https://interoperability.blob.core.windows.net/files/MS-DOCX/%5BMS-DOCX%5D.pdf>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
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Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	.docx reports are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
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How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	.docx versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
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What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Building information data and reports should be preserved indefinitely.
--	---

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
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DATA COLLECTION 8

How will the data be collected or created?	GIS data editing (ESRI ArcGIS Pro)
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What data will you collect or create?	.geojson
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Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>GeoJSON, short for Geographic JavaScript Object Notation, is an open standard format for representing geospatial data structures using JSON (JavaScript Object Notation). It is widely used for encoding and exchanging geographic information in a human-readable and machine-friendly format.</p> <p>In GeoJSON, geographic features are represented as JavaScript objects, making it easy to work with geospatial data in web applications and other software environments. Common types of features include points, lines, and polygons, each defined by a set of coordinates.</p> <p>The simplicity and flexibility of GeoJSON make it a popular choice for sharing geospatial data on the web. It is commonly used in web mapping applications to display interactive maps, display location-based information, and facilitate data exchange between different systems.</p> <p>GeoJSON supports not only basic geometry but also properties that can be associated with each feature. For example, a GeoJSON feature representing a city might include properties such as its name, population, and administrative division.</p> <p>Overall, GeoJSON provides a lightweight and versatile means of representing geospatial data, making it accessible to a wide range of developers and applications, from simple web maps to complex geospatial analysis tools.</p> <p>Technical Documentation: https://stevage.github.io/geojson-spec/</p>
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Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
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How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
---	---------------------

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have
--	--

	access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
--	--

How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL
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Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	.geojson versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
--	---

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	GIS data in geojson should be preserved indefinitely.
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Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
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Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
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Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
--	------------------------

DATA COLLECTION 9

How will the data be collected or created?	Environmental data processing (Microsoft Excel)
--	---

What data will you collect or create?	.csv
---------------------------------------	------

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>The CSV file format is one of the simplest formats for representing structured data, playing a critical role in data management and information exchange.</p> <p>A comma-separated values (CSV) file (.csv) is a type of delimited text file that uses commas or other characters to separate fields. CSV data can contain spatial data as numbers (e.g., longitude and latitude), as text (e.g., Well-Known Text (WKT), GeoJSON, or EsriJSON), or as encoded binary values.</p> <p>Technical Description: https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000323.shtml</p>
--	--

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
-------------------------------------	---------------------

How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
---	---------------------

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
--	---

How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
--	--

Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	csv versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
--	--

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Environmental data in csv should be preserved indefinitely.
--	---

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
---	---

Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
---	-----------------------------

Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
--	------------------------

DATA COLLECTION 10

How will the data be collected or created?	GIS data editing (Google Earth Pro)
--	-------------------------------------

What data will you collect or create?	.kml
---------------------------------------	------

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>A .kmz file is a compressed format of a Keyhole Markup Language (KML) file. These files store important geographic coordinates, such as place markers, shapes, images, or any data that can be displayed on a map.</p> <p>KMZ files are very similar to ZIP files. They allow you to package multiple files together, and they compress the contents to make downloading faster. This allows you to bundle images along with your KML file if you want.</p> <p>You can easily create KMZ files using Google Earth. When you save a placemark or folder from your Places panel you have the choice to save your content as a KMZ file or a KML file.</p> <p>Technical Description: https://developers.google.com/kml/documentation/kmzarchives</p>
--	---

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
-------------------------------------	---------------------

How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
---	---------------------

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
--	---

How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
--	--

Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	.kmz versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
--	---

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	GIS data in kmz should be preserved indefinitely.
--	---

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
---	---

Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
---	-----------------------------

Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
--	------------------------

DATA COLLECTION 11

How will the data be collected or created?	Biodiversity Data (Microsoft Excel)
--	-------------------------------------

What data will you collect or create?	.xlsx
---------------------------------------	-------

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>XLSX is a well-known format for Microsoft Excel documents that was introduced by Microsoft with the release of Microsoft Office 2007. Based on structure organized according to the Open Packaging Conventions as outlined in Part 2 of the OOXML standard ECMA-376, the new format is a zip package that contains a number of XML files. The underlying structure and files can be examined by simply unzipping the .xlsx file.</p> <p>A blank workbook, when extracted to its files, has the following constituent files and folders:</p>
--	--

- [Content_Types].xml – Content types for parts within the package
- _rels (Folder) - Relationships folder
- docProps - overall document properties
- xl (Folder), including:
 - _rels
 - theme
 - worksheets
 - styles.xml
 - workbook.xml

Technical documentation:

<https://interoperability.blob.core.windows.net/files/MS-XLSX/%5bMS-XLSX%5d.pdf>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
-------------------------------------	---------------------

How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
---	---------------------

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	<p>Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).</p>
--	--

How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
--	--

Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	xlsx versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
--	---

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Biodiversity data in xlsx should be preserved indefinitely.
--	---

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
---	---

Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
---	-----------------------------

Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
--	------------------------

DATA COLLECTION 12

How will the data be collected or created?	Geographic raster data
--	------------------------

What data will you collect or create?	.GeoTIFF
---------------------------------------	----------

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>GeoTIFF is format extension for storing georeference and geocoding information in a TIFF 6.0 compliant raster file by tying a raster image to a known model space or map projection. The GeoTIFF format uses a defined set of TIFF tags to describe cartographic information associated with TIFF imagery that originates from satellite imaging systems, scanned aerial photography, scanned maps, digital elevation models, or as a result of geographic analyses.</p>
--	---

GeoTIFF can store a broad range of georeferencing information, catering to geographic as well as projected coordinate systems needs.

Technical documentation:

<https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000279.shtml>

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage ethical issues?	Specified in the GA
-------------------------------------	---------------------

How will you manage copyright and IPR issues?	Specified in the GA
---	---------------------

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	Datasets are stored on the project cloud folder when the respective task is completed by the team members who have access to the storage space, following the relevant naming convention (see ANNEX).
--	---

How will you manage access and security?	Project cloud space on Cyl's HPCF is accessible through user authentication (nextcloud service). B_GREEN platform is accessible through user authentication service URL.
--	--

Selection and Preservation

Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	GeoTIFF versions of design R&D should be retained and preserved following the naming convention.
--	--

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	Geographic raster data in GeoTIFF should be preserved indefinitely.
--	---

Data Sharing

Are any restrictions on data sharing required? How will you share the data?	To be shared only with team members signed an NDA. To be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository.
---	---

Responsibilities and Resources

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Cloud space provided by HO.
---	-----------------------------

Who will be responsible for data management?	Project officer of HO.
--	------------------------

Data open access and sharing

The authors of any work that makes substantial use of the data must communicate with the data source prior to publication. The data will be quality controlled, by the respective B_GREEN partnership member. The B_GREEN consortium retains all Intellectual Property Rights.

5. Network Storage

Documentation of user access to network storage through OpenSSH Authentication Agent, published at <https://hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/documentation/login.html> (below, screenshot of first page of the documentation that captures the contents of the HPCF documentation).

The screenshot shows the 'HPC Access and Login' page from The Cyprus Institute's HPCF documentation. The page is titled 'HPC Access and Login' and is part of a larger documentation set. The navigation menu includes: HOME PAGE, ABOUT US, SERVICES, RESOURCES, DOCUMENTATION, CONTACT, and SUPPORT. The main content area is divided into three columns:

- Left Column (Navigation):**
 - HPCF Documentation
 - Home
 - HPC Access and Login
 - Data transfer
 - Environment and Modules
 - Running jobs >
 - Software >
 - Useful commands
 - Nextcloud Access and Login
- Center Column (Main Content):**

HPC Access and Login

Obtaining an account

To gain access to one of the HPC systems you must first apply for Preparatory or Production Access. More details on how to do that can be found in the "Apply" page.

Upon acceptance of your application you should request an account following the below steps:

 - If this is the first time you are applying for access you need to submit the "Request an account" form through our helpdesk system's portal. You first need to create an account to the portal and then proceed with completing the below form:

Request an account

 - If you already have an account on one of our HPC systems and you would like to associate your existing account with a new project you need to submit the "Add existing user account to project" form:

Add existing user account to project

-For Production Access, as "Proposal ID" put the project code (eg. lspre100s1) corresponding to your application submission in the Linkings system. For Preparatory or Educational access as "Project ID" type the ticket number e.g. "HPCF-1510". For other access type "Other Access".

Please note:

 - You will not be granted a user account on a HPC resource if you have not completed this form.
 - Each accepted project is allocated a specific HPC site, you will only be allowed access to your projects allocated site(s)
 - You will not be granted access unless you are registered as a collaborator in an accepted production or preparatory project. Additional collaborators (not registered in the original proposal) can only be registered by the project leader by contacting hpc.support@cyi.ac.cy
 - If you are permitted access to more than one HPC resource you will have to complete the form for each permitted site &€" each time choosing the appropriate (and different) HPC resource you are entitled to use. Once the above has been done, you will be contacted by the HPC Facility team for your login details.

Generating SSH keys

In order to generate a SSH key pair follow the below steps:

Linux/Mac

Create a public and private key pair using the following command:

```
ssh-keygen
```

You will be prompted for a filename for saving the private key. You should press Enter to use the default name: /home/username/.ssh/id_rsa

You will be prompted for a password to protect your private key which you will also confirm. ALWAYS use such a password to protect your private key. ssh-keygen will then create a private and public key. The public key will have a .pub extension (e.g., id_rsa.pub)
- Right Column (Table of contents):**

Table of contents

 - Obtaining an account
 - Generating SSH keys
 - Linux/Mac
 - Windows
 - Using PuTTYgen
 - Using OpenSSH
 - HPC systems hostnames
 - HPC systems login
 - Linux/Mac
 - Windows
 - Using PuTTY
 - Using OpenSSH

More documentation to be found at

https://hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/documentation/nextcloud_access_login.html

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HOME PAGE ABOUT SERVICES RESOURCES DOCUMENTATION CONTACT SUPPORT

HPCF Documentation

- Home
- HPC Access and Login
- Data transfer
- Environment and Modules
- Running jobs >
- Software >
- Useful commands
- Nextcloud Access and Login

Nextcloud with rclone

Setting up rclone

Users may also use the Rclone tool to copy their data from/to their nextcloud account with ease

To install and setup rclone for your computer follow the instructions below:

Install rclone using the command

```
sudo apt install rclone
```

Configure rclone to work with Nextcloud:

Start with the following command

```
rclone config
```

Then follow the steps below:

- Firstly you will be asked to input a name for the remote host. You can just type **Nextcloud** (but you may name it however you like)
- You will now be asked to input a type of storage to configure. Type **webdav** .
- Now you will be asked to input the URL of the host to connect to. Here type **https://drive.hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/remote.php/webdav/**.
- Next you should enter the name of the Webdav site/service/software you are using. Type **nextcloud**.
- After that you should input your Nextcloud account's username.
- Then to type your account's password you need to type **y** for the next question in order to manually type down your password.
- Type the password twice to confirm it.
- For the bearer token you are asked afterwards, you can just hit enter as it is optional and type **n** for the next question as well
- Finally review the information you typed and choose **y** if it is correct so that the new remote is added. You have now connected your Nextcloud account with rclone

Table of contents

- Nextcloud with rclone
- Setting up rclone
- Using rclone

Data transfer to network storage through SCP & RSYNC, published at https://hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/documentation/data_transfer.html (below, screenshot of first page of the documentation that captures the contents of the HPCF documentation).

HPCF Documentation

- Home
- HPC Access and Login
- [Data transfer](#)
- Environment and Modules
- Running jobs >
- Software >
- Useful commands
- Nextcloud Access and Login

Data transfer

Data transfer

All users have the option to transfer files to and from the systems. Instructions on how to do that can be found below.

Linux/Mac

The two most common commands you can use for data transfers over SSH:

- **scp**: for the full transfer of files and directories (only works fine for single files or directories of small/trivial size).
- **rsync**: a software application which synchronizes files and directories from one location to another while minimizing data transfer as only the outdated or inexistent elements are transferred (practically required for lengthy complex transfers, which are more likely to be interrupted in the middle). Of both, normally the second approach should be preferred, as more generic; note that, both ensure a secure transfer of the data, within an encrypted tunnel.

Table of contents

- Data transfer
- Linux/Mac
 - Using scp
 - Using rsync
- Windows

6. Data security and privacy

Data security and privacy will be ensured using the authorization and authentication infrastructure that will be offered by the cloud service provided by the project HO at the Cyl's HPCF.

6.a. Privacy and Ethical Aspects

Researchers commit this project to fully comply with the applicable ethical principles from EU legislation, which is nationally endorsed. The specific legislation that applies to our research and communication tasks are Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (EC, 1995) and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (EU, 2000).

Ethical issues, specifically those involving volunteers for environmental, urban and social science research, are an integral part of the methodology, specifically of data management and knowledge dissemination activities. Accordingly, researchers will manage and supervise so that there are no potential risks (for individuals and communities/society alike) in core and transversal tasks, and that it will not be necessary to minimise potential harm in this proposal. The research may raise some sensitive issues (such as observation of places or people's opinions) and the researchers will inform the volunteers about their rights in protection and privacy issues before any public activity is undertaken. Surveys will have an initial statement specifying that the volunteers consent to their anonymous data to be used just for research purposes. Interviews will provide a space to allocate their signature and national ID number to clearly document that they are informed in advance.

About data ethics, all main partners in this project have an online repository of multidisciplinary research datasets, hosted by a data library in information services. It acts as a trusted repository, ensuring that research data will be preserved. Universitat Jaume I (<http://repositori.uji.es/xmlui/>), University Naples (<https://www.iris.unina.it/>), Itecons (<https://www.itecons.uc.pt/services/publications>) and Cyprus Institute website have their own systems of open-access repository.

Any private data that may be collected will be with the permission of the building owner and are only accessible by the Administrator and the respective Municipality, which already has access to said data by law, e.g. in Cyprus, through the planning permit procedure

(http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/tph/tph.nsf/ishippodamos_en/ishippodamos_en?OpenDocument);

http://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/tph/tph.nsf/lawsregulations_en/lawsregulations_en?opendocument),.

In Spain data will be collected from the cadaster open source data: [Sede Electrónica del Catastro - Inicio](#); and from the open source data of the National Statistics Institute: [INE. Instituto Nacional de Estadística](#). So access to private data is not foreseen.

In Portugal data will be collected from the open source data: [European Space Agency \(ESA\) – Copernicus DEM](#); [OpenStreetMap for Land Use/Land Cover Production](#); and from the open source data of [Data Centre of the Directorate-General for Territory \(DGT\)](#). Will also be collected from the Municipality City of Coimbra database. Data will also be collected from the internal Coimbra City Council database, ensuring that only non-private data is shared. So access to private data is not foreseen.

In Italy data will be equally collected from the cadaster open source data: [Agenzia delle Entrate - Consultazione cartografia catastale](#); from the open source data of the [National Statistics Institute: ISTAT - Istituto Nazionale di Statistica](#); and from the [Geoportal of the Metropolitan City of Naples](#); So access to private data is not foreseen.

Free to access urban datasets will be included in the B_GREEN platform for demonstration purposes. These data will be open to the public as they contain no private information and describe public information about the buildings that were provided by the various Municipal Authorities engaged in B_GREEN. Every possible effort was made by the surveyors collecting the data to remove any private information from the representations of the urban built environment that is published, as well as of the natural environment in public open spaces.

7. Implementation of FAIR Data Principles

7.a. Findability

7.a.i. Persistent Identification

Following the policy of the Cyl Data repository, a unique and persistent data object identifier (DOI) is assigned on each dataset requiring long term preservation, to ensure sustainability and consistency of access.

7.a.ii. Naming conventions

Related to cloud storage, project team members are encouraged to choose meaningful names so that the content is immediately apparent to others in the future. It is recommended to avoid the usage of spaces in directory and file names and using hyphens and underscores instead. Those naming conventions defined for the network storage also serve the purpose of ensuring inherent cross-platform compatibility. For communicating paths to locations on the network storage, the *Naming Convention* as described in ANNEX, here, is recommended, for which the above naming conventions ensure a unified and clear format.

7.a.iii. Versioning

For B_GREEN, every data set is initially created in a draft stage (called DRAFT) in which it is only visible to project members. Authors can modify data sets in draught stage ad libitum without any publicly visible effects. A version number and a DOI are assigned to the data set every time it is published, but only after passing the review process by the project PI. Finally, the dataset is published to Cyl's data repository (<https://www.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/dareclimed-data-repository.html>) & on Zenodo project space (<https://zenodo.org/communities/1013140rg221727303689/?page=1&size=20>). Once a version of a data set has been published, it remains publicly available.

7.a.iv. Metadata

The annotation of metadata for data sets residing on the network storage is left to the researcher's responsibility as an optional preparatory work for later publishing. It is recommended to store all available metadata in separate files next to the data sets.

For B_GREEN, providing metadata for new data sets is mandatory and technically enforced. Metadata are organized in different metadata blocks accounting for the fact that different research disciplines require different metadata. The citation metadata block needs to be provided for all data sets. The following fields of the citation metadata block are required and automatically added by the software:

- DOI;
- The name of the person who deposited the dataset;
- The date the dataset was added.

Within the citation metadata block, it is technically enforced that authors provide the following fields:

- The title of the dataset;
- The author (name);
- A textual description of the dataset;
- One or more keywords describing important aspects of the data (Authors are encouraged to use a standardized keyword vocabulary whenever possible);
- The grant information, with the grant agency;
- The project information, as used in the project proposal.

Authors are encouraged to provide the following information if applicable and available:

- The time period during which the data set was collected or produced (in the citation block);
- Other metadata blocks, namely the process block describing the way the data was produced and the metadata for research software block, which must contain information about the software that was used.

7.b. Accessibility

7.b.i. Repositories

All project data and associated metadata and documentation that are not disclosed by IPR are stored in the HO's data repository (<https://repository.cyi.ac.cy/>) and will become publicly available on Zenodo wherever possible. Besides, all four main partners participating in this project join or are aligned with the HRS4R programme on the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r/awarded>). B_GREEN sources will be published in open repositories such as Zenodo (EU OpenAIRE) where we will create a project community and be widely disseminated through the consortium partnership networks.

7.b.ii. Access Restrictions

All data produced will be subject to limited access due to pending restrictions. Restricted data to be shared only with team members signed the GA. Data to be stored on a project folder on HPCF and dataset to be uploaded with restricted access on Cyl data repository. Access restriction can be applied on the data set level as well as on a per-file level.

7.b.iii. Tools and Documentation

In order to connect to the cloud storage, the only requirement is a file browser which is part of any operating system. Access to data deposited on the Cyl data repository requires no other tools than a web browser. The tools required to work with the actual files deposited in the repository depend on the data set. Data of B_GREEN shall be deposited in file formats as described in the respective section (cf. **Data Summary**).

Authors are required to provide at least a free-text description of the data as part of the metadata blocks. This description should enable external users to understand (i) what experiment, simulation, etc. the data set is from, (ii) what the independent and dependent factors measured/computed in the data set are and (iii) how these factors can be accessed in the files deposited in the data set. Authors are encouraged to provide a structured documentation of the data, for instance in the respective metadata blocks of [select accordingly: e57, dwg, shp, pdf, xlsx, doc, jpg].

7.c. Interoperability

7.c.i. Data Formats

Authors in B_GREEN shall use file formats widely used in the respective application domain when depositing their data. Where bespoke software is required to effectively use the data, authors should preferably convert the data into a widely used file format or provide the required software on a publicly accessible source code repository like GitHub / Zenodo and link to that repository in the metadata of the data set.

Table 1. File formats for commonly used data types.

Data type Preferred format(s)	Data type Preferred format(s)
Formatted text PDF/A – ISO 19005 (.pdf)	Formatted text PDF/A – ISO 19005 (.pdf)
Plain text UTF-8-encoded text files (.txt)	Plain text UTF-8-encoded text files (.txt)
Spreadsheets / database	Comma-separated values – UTF-8 (.csv)
Bitmap images	Portable Network Graphics (.png) Windows Bitmap (.bmp) JPEG (.jpg) TIFF (.tiff)
Vector graphics	Scalable Vector Graphics (.svg) Encapsulated PostScript (.eps) Adobe Illustrator (.ai)
Video	MPEG-4 – H.264, H.265 (.mp4) MPEG-2 (.mp2) RIFF AVI (.avi) QuickTime (.mov)
Presentations	Office Open XML – ISO/IEC 29500 (.pptx) OpenDocument – ISO/IEC 26300 (.odp) PDF/A – ISO 19005 (.pdf)
3D modelling	3ds max (.max)
Construction drawings	ASCII files, DWG & DXF International Foundation Class (.IFC)
GIS	shp SLPK

Table 2. Data Types Formats

Type	Source	Format	Size Estimation
3D files	Designs, site documentation	.fbx, .obj, .skp, .dwg	< 100 GB
Audio	Meeting and interview recordings	.mp3, .aac	< 1 GB
GIS data	Geospatial vectors, maps	.shp, .kmz, .las, .laz, .zlas	< 20 GB
Graphics	Photographs, drawings, images, maps	.png, .jpeg, .jpg, .tiff, .pdf	< 150 GB
Interactive data	Surveys, quizzes, feedback forms from websites	.html, .json	< 0.5 GB
Presentations	Slides of meetings, workshops and seminars	.pptx, .odp	< 0,5 GB
Remote sensing data	Airborne photos, LIDAR, LANDSAT and SENTINEL images	.las, laz., zlas, .vlr, .jpg	< 150 GB
Spreadsheets	Surveys responses	.xlsx, .xml, .ods, .fods, .csv	< 0,5 GB
Text	Text deliverables, interviews, notes from workshops and seminars, articles, blog posts, guidelines	.doc, .docx, .odt, .txt, .pdf	< 1 GB
Video	Recordings	.mp4, .flv, .avi	< 200 GB
Website	Webpages, posts	.html	< 1 GB

7.c.ii. Metadata

B_GREEN authors are encouraged to use standardized vocabularies for keywords (such as the ISO 6707-1:2020, the European Standard BS 6100-0:2010 or others listed in the Metadata Standards Directory) whenever such standardized keywords are available for the research topic.

7.c.iii. Review Process

The data curator (HO designated person) can either return the data set to the author in order to resolve open issues or mark it as ready for publication. The Cyl's Research & Innovation Management Support office provides checklists for authors and curators making sure that all important aspects ranging from copyright law over privacy and potential non-disclosure agreements to the completeness of the actual data and metadata are covered in the review process in a transparent manner.

7.d. Reusability

7.d.i. Licensing

A license needs to be specified when publishing data. This way, it is ensured that third parties always know the conditions under which the published data sets may be reused. Most B_GREEN datasets are subject to legal or contractual obligations that prohibit authors from assigning a public license key.

7.d.ii. Embargo Periods

An embargo period for all datasets applies until the related scientific publication has been accepted for publication, while indefinite time extended embargo period is imposed to all datasets related to/subject to patent applications.

7.d.iii. Retention Period

The Cyl commits to ensuring the continued availability of the cloud storage (Cyl data repository) until the end of the final funding period of B_GREEN. Related to all data sets published in Zenodo this commitment applies independently from the duration of B_GREEN.

7.d.iv. Contact Information

For each published dataset, a functional e-mail address or the e-mail address of an employee with a permanent labour contract as contact address should be specified to ensure that third parties are able to contact the depositors of a data set. In case of B_GREEN, the e-mail address of one of the principal investigators involved in the production of the data set shall be specified as contact.

7.d.v. Allocation of Resources: Cost

The operating cost for data deposited in the cloud storage is estimated by Cyl's HPCF to be around 0.50€ per Gigabyte every five years. These costs are covered by the annual budget of the HO/Cyl.

7.d.vi. Roles

Associate Professor G. Artopoulos acts as the person responsible for coordinating the research data management efforts within the research project. As part of this role, he is responsible to keep this data management plan updated as changes in data and processing strategies occur.

Conclusions

The DMP is a living document that will evolve as the project progresses and as new information on data collection, generation, and handling emerges. Day-to-day data management activities will be carried out following the procedures and methods described in this document, in collaboration with the Project Coordinator, the Data Manager and the Data Management Team indicated above. Two updated and expanded versions of the DMP will be prepared and submitted in months 18 and 30, which will depict the current state of data management within the project.

The Project Coordinator and the Data Manager will jointly ensure that any data management issues which may arise during the project will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

Bibliography

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- ISO 19650-1. 2018. ISO 19650-1:2018 Organization and Digitization of Information about Buildings and Civil Engineering Works, Including Building Information Modelling (BIM) — Information Management Using Building Information Modelling — Part 1: Concepts and Principles.
- Ryan, Emily M., and Thomas F. Sanquist. 2012. 'Validation of Building Energy Modeling Tools under Idealized and Realistic Conditions'. *Energy and Buildings* 47 (April): 375–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.12.020>.

ANNEX I

Name Convention

A general name coding has been set for the internal needs of the B_GREEN project.

The name will be composed of single fields of code, representing file's metadata so that the name itself will provide information without the file being opened. Names should be created by joining together the codes in the specified fields, in the specified order, using the "-" hyphen character.

Model Naming Conventions

Names should be created by joining together codes in the specified field, in the specified order, using only the "-" hyphen character, which is therefore not allowed in any code. All letters will be in uppercase.

No spacing between elements should use.

The use of ":" and "-" are prohibited in the field code.

The "-" has to be used for the separation between fields.

Note: If any description is optionally append it shall be preceded by an underscore "_". The hyphen character should not be used in a description field. The descriptive text should not be used to imply further distinction of meaning.

General Naming Convention

- Field 1: Project (BG – B_GREEN)
 - An abbreviated code or number identifying the project.
- Field 2: Location (up to 4 characters)
 - Identifier of which historical area the file relates to.
 - Cuenca: CU; Naples: NAP; Coimbra: CO; Nicosia: NIC
- Field 3: Work Package and Project deliverable or milestone (5 characters)
 - An abbreviated code identifying the originating Work package and the relative project deliverable or milestone.
- Field 3: Partner (Recommended 4 characters)
 - An abbreviated code identifying the originating stakeholder or Partner.UJI; Itecons; UNINA; CYI
- Field 4: Description (optional)
 - Descriptive field to define the type of data portrayed in the file. Avoid repeating information codified in other fields. Can be used to describe

any part of the previous fields, or to further clarify any other aspect of the contained data. In case the file is related to a cultural heritage building or street the BG team shall fill in this field the building/plot code.

- Field 5: Type of document
 - For example, Point cloud, Model, csv, etc.

- Field 6: Revision
 - Descriptive field to define the revision of the file. Could be WIP01 in case of a “working in progress” asset, and the first revision.
 - Work in progress: WIP
 - Shared: SHR
 - Published: PUB
 - Archive: ARC

Example: Model File Name Description

BG_NIC_3D.02_CYI_Model_WIP

Table 3. File Type Codification

Code	Type Content
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
E57	Vendor-neutral Point Cloud Format
...	...
SHP	GIS vector objects
SLPK	3D GIS
DWG	Autocad File Format
DWF/ DWFx	Autodesk Design Review File
PDF	PDF File Format
JPG	Image File
XLSX	Microsoft Excel File Format
DOC	Microsoft Word File Format
QGZ	QGIS working file
PY	Python for QGIS script
TIF	Raster files
CSV	Extracted data
	R model

ANNEX II

Zenodo upload instructions

Public data collected/generated throughout the project should be uploaded to the certified Zenodo repository that supports the Open Data policy for EC funded research. This includes public deliverables, public data/datasets and scientific publications. These should be uploaded by all team members generating data. To successfully upload data to the B_GREEN community of Zenodo, one must execute the following steps.

1. Create an account in Zenodo, which is free of charge (this step is only required if you don't already have an account).
2. Log in to your account.
3. Navigate to the B_GREEN community
 - a. either by clicking on 'Communities' and performing search using the term 'B_GREEN'
 - b. or by directly using in the browser the URL
['https://zenodo.org/communities/b_green/'](https://zenodo.org/communities/b_green/)
4. Click the 'New upload' button.
5. Choose the files that you want to upload.
6. In the 'Communities' box, make sure that the project's community is already selected (you should see the logo and title).
7. It is also required to add the community 'European Commission Funded Research'. You can locate it through the search box and add it by clicking on it. If both communities are selected, data will automatically be uploaded to both of them.
8. Select the type of upload and after filling in the necessary metadata fields, click 'Upload' to complete the procedure.